

THE PRACTICAL WAYS FOR IMPROVING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article deals with numerous reasonable and practical ways of boosting listening skills in the English language. Also, all suggested methods and solutions are based on reliable facts and details. They will be supported with solid reasons as well as examples.

Keywords: English language, listening skills, listening comprehension, dictation, note-taking, new words, watching movies, audio, concentration.

ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ СПОСОБЫ УЛУЧШЕНИЯ НАВЫКОВ АУДИРОВАНИЯ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются многочисленные разумные и практические способы улучшения навыков аудирования на английском языке. Также все предлагаемые методы и решения основаны на достоверных фактах и деталях. Они будут подкреплены вескими доводами и примерами.

Ключевые слова: Английский язык, навыки аудирования, понимание на слух, диктовка, конспектирование, новые слова, просмотр фильмов, аудио, концентрация.

INTRODUCTION

Today English language is widely spoken and taught all over the world, therefore it is considered as an international language. It is being used in various kinds of fields namely diplomacy, science, technology, tourism as well as it is the language of the social media. These days, there are a number of English proficiency tests such as IELTS and TOEFL, which assess the language ability of people who want to continue their studies or work in a country where English is the language of communication. These testing systems tests students' four skills: listening, reading, writing and speaking. However, language learners are facing with many issues in the process of acquiring these skills, especially, with listening ability. This article mainly focuses on the importance of listening comprehension in English, the major problems associated with this skill and highlights all possible and viable solutions to the improvement of listening.

MAIN BODY

Listening is a process that includes hearing sounds and comprehend their meaning. However, English learning students encounter with several problems related to this skill. All of these issues will be highlighted one by one.

First one is being unfamiliar with new words which leads them to misinterpret what they listen. Simply put, if a student has a limited range of vocabulary, he or she cannot get the main point of the meaning properly. Therefore, having poor vocabulary resource makes this learning process more difficult.

The next problem is the concentration matter. To exemplify, in the process of doing listening activities and exercises, many language learners are not able to concentrate on all parts

equally. The reason why is that, unless students understand one word's meaning or found one part unclear, they cannot move on to the next sentences and they keep thinking of this statement. This causes them to concentrate only one part of the script, not fully.

Another major issue is the lack of overall listening comprehension. It is about understanding and making sense of recording or spoken language by listening. Recognizing context is absolutely important in comprehension as it relates meanings to the real world and daily lives. However, many students are struggling with enhancing comprehension in listening and catching a clear meaning.

As for practical solutions to tackle, there are numerous ways to highlight. To overcome the problem of dealing with new vocabularies in listening process, **“Dictation” method** is highly suggested. Dictation is a type of method to boost listening skill and to enlarge vocabulary resource by listening and writing down what you hear. In order to do dictation in a correct way, there are three main steps to complete.

1. Audio should be played and students should listen the first sentence of the script and pause;
2. Then, the students ought to type what they listen on computer or write with pen on paper;
3. After writing process, written work should be checked with correct tape scripts.

When it comes to this **method's benefits**, many of them are worth mentioning. Initially, while doing dictation, language learners face with new vocabularies and they will underline or circle these kinds of words. In a subsequent step, checking process occurs and all new words will be translated into students' own native language. By doing so, they will have a chance to memorize them while practicing. If dictation is done on a daily basis regularly, lexical resource of students will be automatically enlarged on different topics. Additional advantage of this technique is enhancing **overall listening comprehension**, because while practicing, learners are made to understand every sentence's meaning one by one. Without catching a main idea, one will not be able to write it down fully.

The next important method is called **“Note-taking”** which is especially necessary for overcoming concentration problem and to tackle difficulties associated with catching specific details while listening audios or spoken language. It is about considering key points and ideas, namely numbers, names, addresses, emails names and other specific information. While implementing this method, take into consideration these following steps:

1. When audio is played or speaker begins speaking, language learners also start taking accurate notes. Notes should involve only short sentences and key points;
2. Full explanations or long descriptions must be omitted, as notes should be to the point;
3. Names of people, places and numbers, addresses also ought to be written down, since these parts can easily refer main idea of the text;
4. At the end, the spelling and grammar must be checked with the correct form of script.

As for its upsides, the first one is definitely related to **concentration**. In order to take notes properly while listening an audio, one must concentrate fully, remain calm and just pay attention to the meaning. By doing so, effective note-taking process occurs. Moreover, students will be more able to **pick specific details** while listening to a speaker or a recording because of this technique which allows every language learner to take bullet-point notes easily and concentrate on the meaning of the played audio on a whole. If every student acquires these skills by practicing mentioned methods, their language proficiency will be higher.

Additional way to boost **overall listening comprehension in English** and enlarging vocabulary range is **watching movies and programs in English** language. By watching foreign language movies, the students will have opportunity to listen English in a natural condition, in an informal form, slang phrases, idioms, native accents and colloquial expressions which cannot be found in the usual dictionaries. It creates a relaxed learning atmosphere among learners. In order to get benefits by watching movies, following steps should be done:

1. An English movie should be chosen according to the students' level of English. If learners' level of English is lower, movies with simpler language must be chosen. But films with advanced language are recommended for students who want to challenge themselves.

2. For more advantage, online scripts of the films can be turned on, therefore it will be easier to comprehend by listening and if there is a new word, one has a chance to pause it and translate or write it down by reading its script.

3. Having a notebook with you while watching English movies is also beneficial, since there will be a lot of new vocabularies, several idioms and different colloquial expressions. When students are not able to translate those phrases properly, they ought to write them down to look up their meaning later. If all of these steps are done in a proper way, many core advantages can be taken.

Finally, **listening English podcasts** continuously during a day will also enhance listening skills. But it should be done regularly, as the more language learners listen to English, the more their brain will be familiar with this language. There are a number of upsides of podcasts, one of the most important benefits is that it is convenient and time-saving in the daily life situations. The reason why is that, all language learners can listen to podcasts while they are doing sport exercises, commuting to workplaces or universities and doing home chores such as cooking, washing or cleaning. By listening podcasts on different topics, learners are exposed to wide range of vocabularies, different kinds of dialects or accents which allow them to be familiar with several listening features.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, there are several difficulties such as limited vocabulary range, poor concentration and lack of comprehension associated with listening skill in English language. However, I am of the opinion that if "Dictation" methods, "Note-taking" techniques are implemented in a proper way and they are blended with listening podcasts and watching English movies, English learning students will have a chance to boost their listening comprehension skills in a faster and easier way. All given methods and solutions are based on hard practice and daily practice which can definitely lead language learners to success.

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